

ReUse: Efficient direct recycling for low-value LFP battery for circular and sustainable waste management

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The rapid rise of electric vehicles (EVs) and renewable energy storage solutions has led to the exponential increase of lithium-ion batteries (LIBs). As these batteries reach the end of their life, efficient and sustainable recycling methods become essential to avoid resource waste and reduce environmental impacts. The ReUse project is dedicated to addressing this challenge by developing new processes for recycling lithium iron phosphate (LFP) batteries, which are expected to dominate a substantial share of the battery market by 2030.

ReUse focuses on direct recycling and reuse of critical battery materials. Unlike traditional pyro- and hydrometallurgical recycling processes, direct recycling is considered to have lower energy requirements, minimal greenhouse gas emissions,

and higher recovery rates of essential battery components, such as graphite, electrolyte, and cathode materials. The extraction and recovery of electrode binders, such as PVDF (polyvinylidene fluoride) used in LFP electrodes, represents a significant innovation in this area. The processes developed in the project are scalable and sustainable, enabling reuse of the recycled materials in the production of new electrodes or other industries, contributing to a near-closed-loop lifecycle for battery components.

Among the project’s key innovations is the automated sorting of end-of-life (EoL) lithium-ion batteries, enabling the systematic separation of valuable active materials with high selectivity, yield, and purity, using automated centrifugation. This process increases material recovery efficiency and improves process water treatment, minimizing waste and optimizing material reuse. In alignment with the EU’s Critical Raw Materials Act, these innovations reduce Europe’s reliance on third-party countries for primary resources, positioning the EU more competitively in the global market and increasing energy autonomy.

For cathode and anode regeneration, electrochemical re-lithiation and microwave-assisted regeneration offer recycling options for LFP materials with 30% energy savings compared to traditional methods. The flexibility of these processes ensures that the maximum amount of valuable materials is reclaimed while waste is kept to a minimum, all without compromising the performance of newly manufactured components.

A comprehensive monitoring framework integrates automated disassembly, selective shredding, and real-time data management, ensuring material traceability and operational efficiency. The recovery of electrolyte

salts and binders supports a more circular battery production system, leading to enhanced speed and precision as well as reduced reliance on new raw materials. The online database created by ReUse will help optimize battery discharging routines, making the reuse of LFP batteries in future applications more efficient.

The performance of recovered functional materials, such as active materials, binders, and electrolytes, is often lower than that of pristine materials. As the ReUse project advances, one potential challenge is their difference in performance. For the EV market, e.g., higher performance thresholds are crucial. However, there are other large markets, like stationary or portable energy storage, where slightly decreased performance may be acceptable compared to the EV sector.

Addressing logistical challenges, the complex notification procedures related to transporting waste batteries within the EU can hinder the efficient delivery of end-of-life (EoL) lithium-ion batteries (LiBs) to recycling facilities. Developing a clear and streamlined shipping strategy is crucial to ensure the timely arrival of materials.

The project aims to increase the global competitiveness of the European battery ecosystem in line with the European Strategic Plan for a clean and sustainable transition towards climate neutrality. Building on the BATTERY 2030+ Initiative's Roadmap and the European Partnership on Batteries, ReUse aims to contribute to the policy needs of the European Green Deal and efficient recycling technologies.

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